

BIOCHEMICAL AND PHYSIOLOGICAL CHANGES IN PARASITE PARAMETERS IN THE HOST- PARASITE RELATIONSHIP

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Annotation This paper presents an analysis of the literature on the study of the diversity of adaptive relationships between the parasite and the host. Changes in protein metabolism pathways at stages of the parasite life cycle are considered. The process of changing the protein composition during the life cycle of the parasite is the highest level of adaptation to changing living conditions. The pharmacological properties of cholinergic receptors in the muscles of round and flat helminths, as well as the muscles of various host organs in which the parasites are localized, are considered. Contractility of the somatic muscles of nematodes and the host intestinal muscles under the influence of acetylcholine and its agonists and contrasting with a decrease in the response of the muscles of flatworms (relaxation) and the intestinal muscles of the bile ducts of the host (contraction) on These substances are considered as a form of physiological adaptation of the nervous system of helminths, which is consolidated during evolution.

Key words: helminth, parasite, metabolism, *Ascaris lumbricoides* ,
Triaenophorus nodulosus , *F. hepatica* .

Introduction. It is known that the organism is a parasite interacts with the host organism in almost any location through external tissues - cuticle or tegument. In the course of evolutionary changes, the external tissues of parasites have acquired a reliable set of molecular mechanisms of defense and aggression, unique for survival and adaptation in the host body. The structure of the surface molecular layer of parasitic organisms is largely determined by the environmental conditions in

which they live and the interaction with the defense systems activated by the host in response to invasion [1].

The formation during evolution of molecular mechanisms of defense and aggression in parasitic organisms, ensuring their survival in the host body, shows the complexity of relationships at the molecular level in the parasitic organism-host system and the inevitability of the emergence of different types of cells [2].

Biochemical adaptation is formed when it is necessary to implement adaptive mechanisms at the cellular level and leads to a change in the activity of existing intracellular enzymes and the emergence of new enzyme systems in a living organism. That is, biochemical adaptation reflects changes in enzymatic and hormonal processes based on the adaptive reactions of the body [1, 3-6].

Material and methods. The object of materials used is a meta-analysis of research results published in leading scientific journals in 2010-2023, analysis results and statistical processing methods.

Results and their analysis. Based on an analysis of the literature, the following conclusions can be drawn about the adaptive processes in the parasite-host relationship: - one of the physiological and biochemical features of helminths is a parasitic lifestyle, especially on the intermediate or main organism of the host; - their infectious (invasive) period - eggs (oncospheres) or larval cysts - the period of hatching of mobile larvae. Invasive periods of parasites entering the host's body through nutrition: from a "quiet" state to an "explosive" period of "development". It is influenced by the temperature of the internal environment of a living organism, enzymes and other bioactive factors. First of all, at normalized temperature the concentration of HCO ions increases 3^- and the egg (oncosphere) is pushed through the shell of the larval cyst into the internal environment, acting as a special receptor on the receptors of the embryo or larva of the egg. helminth As a result, the biosynthesis of special juices (enzymes) begins, such as chitinase , leucenaminopentidase , esterase . In turn, during the activity of enzymes, the shell of the helminth egg, the cyst (sac) of the infestation larva dissolves, and the

infestation larva comes out, settles in the tissues of the internal environment of the host, begins postembryonic or imaginal development, feeds, differentiates, and the adult larva (larvocyst) becomes into the stage of parasitic helminth. This is a biochemical description of the adaptation to life of an anaerobic organism and a feature of the metabolism and energy of helminths. In particular, a sharp increase in carbon-water metabolism, a variety of final metabolic products, an increase in the activity of certain enzyme systems in adulthood, a rapid increase in protein biosynthesis for rapid growth, development and leaving a large number of offspring are the main signs of helminth adaptation to parasitic life. Cellular mitochondria that provide biological oxidation of consumed nutrients in the “respiratory chain”, trematodes (for example, *Fasciola hepatica*) are present in the cells of all parts of the body, as well as in other nematodes (for example, *Fasciola hepatica*). *Ascaris lumbricoides* human), are found predominantly in contractile muscle tissue, found in large quantities in cells, as well as in cestodes (for example, human and rat worms - *Hymenolepis diminuta*), small amounts are found in sarcoplasmic cells of muscle fibers. Accordingly, in helminths it was found that all enzymes of the Krebs chain are present, but their activity is very low.

Tissues of living organisms, including parasites. Metabolism, contraction, growth and reproduction of muscle tissue are associated with the activity of proteins. Helminths are characterized by high productivity. For example, *Ascaris lumbricoides*. It has been established that the female nematode lays an average of 200,000 eggs per day, which requires intensive protein biosynthesis in the body and, accordingly, the availability of amino acid reserves. Some differences have been identified between individual proteins of helminths and their hosts. For example, the cuticle protein of roundworms is neither collagen nor keratin in its chemical structure. The main and, perhaps, the only source of protein formation in the body are amino acids obtained from protein foods. There is a lot of information in the literature about the amino acid composition of proteins of representatives of all classes of parasites [2, 7-9].

It is of interest to study the features of the neurochemical basis of life of parasites of different taxa, including the pharmacological properties of the nervous and muscle tissues of parasitic worms; identification of physiologically active substances in these structures - neurotransmitters, acting as chemical transmitters of nerve impulses, the influence of the latter on the effector cell; identify inhibitors, activators, modulators and other participants in mediator processes. The knowledge obtained in this area about parasitic organisms, in comparison with similar information available about their host organism, comes closer to understanding or understanding the complex physiological mechanisms of adaptation of the nervous and muscular systems of parasitic organisms to environmental conditions. In addition, such information can serve as a navigator for the creation of a new generation of targeted anthelmintic drugs [1, 10].

Another type of physiological adaptation noted during the coevolution of the parasite-host system is the cestode *Triaenophorus nodulosus*. and its latest host, cancer, can be considered an example. It has been established that severe infection of crayfish with this helminth (up to 200 parasites in one fish) leads not only to the death of the host, but also to its exhaustion. Moreover, the low pathogenicity of the parasitic organism for the host is associated with a high level of adaptation that has developed during the evolution of the parasite-host system and is aimed at preserving the life of both partners of this balanced system [2, 11].

The muscles of flatworms differ from the muscles of nematodes and most motor muscles of other invertebrates and vertebrates in that they relax in response to acetylcholine and its analogues, as well as in the form of the reaction. Cholinoreception in the muscles of trematodes, especially *F. hepatica*, similar to muscarinic cholinoreception in the host's biliary muscles.

Conclusion. Thus, in the process of mutual adaptation of the parasite and the host organism, the likelihood of maintaining a continuous development cycle of the parasite and preserving the species as a whole increases. sharp increase. Although a deviation from this rule is possible, it depends on the influence of unfavorable

internal and external factors that reduce host resistance, as well as on individual physiological parameters (age, gender, immunological state, etc.).

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